

Understanding Human Factors Influencing Cyber Security in Educational Institutions at Bharatpur Metropolitan City Area

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Abstract

"Human Factors Influencing Cyber Security in Educational Institutions" refers to the various psychological, behavioural, and organisational elements that impact the effectiveness of cybersecurity measures within educational settings. This study aimed to assess the impact of different factors (cyber threat landscape, human errors, password management, vendors and third-party risks) and their impact within educational institutions in Bharatpur Metropolitan City.

Our study applied a quantitative approach to understanding the opinions and experiences of undergraduate students and collected data from two hundred and ten (N = 210) undergraduate students from different IT-related educational institutions of Bharatpur Metropolitan City. The random sampling method is used to select the sample population of this study. This study's ethical issues were carefully considered during the research process.

Our study would indicate the associations between cyber threat landscape, human errors, password management, vendors and third-party risks and their impact on institutional performance. By identifying and addressing issues such as human errors, password management practices, and risks associated with vendors and third-party entities, educational institutions can better protect their digital assets and sensitive information from cyber threats.

This understanding can lead to the implementation of targeted cybersecurity measures and training programs tailored to address specific vulnerabilities, ultimately helping to safeguard the integrity and confidentiality of data within the educational sector in Bharatpur Metropolitan City.

Keywords: *cyber security, educational institutions, cyber threat landscape, human errors, password management, vendors and third-party risks*